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In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices

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Executive summary

In a *transcatheter aortic valve implantation* (TAVI) procedure, the native aortic valve is replaced by an artificial valve prosthesis. One of the objectives of SIMCor is to develop a simulation workflow to estimate TAVI treatment effects on large virtual patient cohorts. As part of this simulation workflow, this deliverable presents a *fast-to-evaluate TAVI deployment model* that provides quantitative insights into the positioning of the implanted device and its effect on post-implantation flow characteristics. The fast-to-evaluate model derives its computational performance from two key simulation technologies, *viz.*: (i) a multi-patch *non-uniform rational b-splines* (NURBS)-based anatomical model, and (ii) a time-dependent discrete contact mechanics model. The NURBS-based geometry description provides a parameterisation of the aorta and the aortic leaflets, from which a set of potential contact points is obtained. The time-dependent mechanical contact model, which solves for the balance of forces, determines the contact points between the TAVI device and the aorta at each time step.

The performance of the developed fast-to-evaluate model is assessed through a series of numerical experiments. A comparison with a high-fidelity finite element simulation (part of *D8.6 - Report on 3D finite element simulation (PHI, M24)*) is presented in this report, demonstrating the ability of the fast-to-evaluate model to predict the global characteristics of the TAVI procedure. Furthermore, a sensitivity analysis of the most important model parameters is considered to demonstrate the robustness of the fast-to-evaluate model. Furthermore, the developed model is used to study the impact of leaflet calcification on the TAVI procedure. Paravalvular leakage areas are compared between a case with and a case without leaflet calcification. The results demonstrate the capability of the fast-to-evaluate model to distinguish between such cases.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
TAVI	Transcatheter Aortic Valve Implantation
NURBS	Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines
IGA	Isogeometric Analysis
STJ	SinoTubular Junction
LVOT	Left Ventricular Outflow Tract
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
ROM	Reduced Order Model
CAD	Computer Aided Graphics

Consortium partners' acronyms

Acronym	Full name
TUE	Technische Universiteit Eindhoven
PHI	Philips Electronics Netherlands B.V.
TUG	Technical University Graz
CHA	Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin
LYN	Lynkeus

Introduction

In the *transcatheter aortic valve implantation* (TAVI) procedure, an artificial valve prosthesis is placed within the native aortic valve, or a previous implant¹. The artificial aortic valve consists of a prosthetic aortic valve and a stent. The stent is crimped before the implantation and placed inside a catheter using a sheath. The catheter is delivered to the intended location using a guidewire under direct image-guidance. When located and orientated in the desired position, the stent is released by pulling the sheath. In the release process, the stent pushes the leaflets toward the walls.

There are several challenges in the TAVI procedure. The work considered herein pertains primarily to the following two challenges: (i) finding an optimal location and orientation is often very difficult², and (ii) calcification of the leaflets can impede the implantation procedure, resulting in undesirable treatment outcomes such as excessive paravalvular leakage³.

Computational models are a useful instrument for attaining insight in and obtaining predictions for the implantation procedure. Several studies have focused on reproducing the TAVI procedure in patient-specific geometries. Auricchio *et al.*⁴ replicated the TAVI placement procedure by simulating all the procedural steps and investigating the effects of model parameters on the stent positioning. The aortic leaflet deformations and calcifications were however not considered in this study. Bianchi *et al.*⁵ and Russ⁶ *et al.* performed a similar study with self-expandable valves and investigated the impact of calcifications and material behaviour on the final deformation patterns. Morganti *et al.*³ replicated TAVI placement with a patient-specific high-fidelity simulation and compared the outcomes with actual post-operational patient data. Within SIMCor, (high-fidelity) models to mimic TAVI deployment and to estimate treatment effects (e.g., paravalvular leakage) are reported in *D9.2 - Device specific models (IIB, M24)* and will be in *D8.7 - Reduced order model (PHI, M30)* by means of high-fidelity finite element analyses.

All the above-described studies pertain to high-fidelity simulations, typically requiring (at least) hours of computation time. This computational cost impedes the direct application of such models in the *virtual research environment* (VRE) envisioned in SIMCor. In this VRE, effective simulations are to be performed on large virtual cohorts. This creates the demand for a *fast-to-evaluate TAVI model*, the development of which has been the primary objective of this deliverable. The positioning of the fast-to-evaluate model in the SIMCor workflow is illustrated in Figure 1. In essence, the idea is that the fast-to-evaluate model takes as input the virtual cohort anatomies generated in WP7. The fast-to-evaluate model then performs a near real-time simulation to attain insights on treatment effects for the virtual cohort. Despite the usage of state-of-the-art simulation technology in the form of spline-based analysis – which will be discussed in detail below – attaining a model that can be evaluated rapidly requires the assumption of model simplifications. The developed fast-to-evaluate model will be discussed in the remainder of this report. A key idea of the developed model is that it facilitates the incorporation of information from high-fidelity simulations (such as the ones reported in *D8.6 - Report on 3D finite element simulation (PHI, M24)*), through the use of *reduced-order models* (ROMs). This approach, which will be at the core of *D8.7* (see Figure 1) allows to consider model improvements without substantially increasing the computation cost of the fast-to evaluate model.

¹ Adams, D. H. *et al.*, 2014, Transcatheter aortic-valve replacement with a self-expanding prosthesis. *New England Journal of Medicine*.

² Fuchs, A. *et al.*, 2018, Commissural alignment of bioprosthetic aortic valve and native aortic valve following surgical and transcatheter aortic valve replacement and its impact on valvular function and coronary filling. *JACC: Cardiovascular Interventions*.

³ Morganti S. *et al.*, 2014, Simulation of transcatheter aortic valve implantation through patient-specific finite element analysis: Two clinical cases, *Journal of Biomechanics*.

⁴ Auricchio F. *et al.*, 2014, Simulation of transcatheter aortic valve implantation: a patient-specific finite element approach, *Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering*.

⁵ Bianchi M. *et al.*, 2015, Simulation of transcatheter aortic valve replacement in patient-specific aortic roots: Effect of crimping and positioning on device performance, 37th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC).

⁶ Russ M. *et al.*, 2015, Simulation of transcatheter aortic valve implantation under consideration of leaflet calcification, 37th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC).

Figure 1: Workflow schematic, outlining the relations between the fast-to-evaluate model considered in this report and the related SIMCor work packages.

The developed fast-to-evaluate model derives its computational speed from two key modelling concepts, both of which will be elaborated below. The first concept is to use splines to attain an accurate, yet low-dimensional (*i.e.*, a limited number of parameters), description of the geometry of the aortic walls and the *moving* leaflets. The developments in this deliverable are based on the experience in our research team with *Isogeometric Analysis* (IGA)⁷, a finite-element-type technique based on splines. The second concept is to describe the contact between the leaflets, the aortic walls, and the expanding stent through a discrete set of point contacts. The time-dependent process of expansion and stent-leaflet-wall interactions is then treated in a semi-explicit manner, enhancing the simulation speed compared to a fully implicit treatment of the geometrically nonlinear problem.

It goes without saying that the modelling assumptions summarised above compromise the level of detail of the results compared to high-fidelity models. This is simply the price one pays for a model that can be evaluated in near real time. From a modelling perspective, the fundamental idea is that the fast-to-evaluate model can still provide valuable information on the treatment effects in terms of its global response characteristics. For example, the positioning and orientation of the implanted stent and its dependence on geometry and possible calcifications should be predictable. The developed model should also present a rough indicator for paravalvular leakage, as this effect has a strong geometric cause. Although the fast-to-evaluate model is not suitable in itself for characterising detailed physical phenomena, such as contact stresses and flow patterns, its global response description should aid in the identification of interesting cases (e.g., cases with high paravalvular leakage areas), and thus in the selection of cases to be investigated with high-fidelity simulations.

The results presented in this report aim to demonstrate the modelling targets set out above. To this end we will consider a comparison study with a result for the high-fidelity simulations performed in D8.6. Moreover, we will study the robustness of the fast-to-evaluate model with respect to its parameters, and we will demonstrate its capability to model the effect of leaflet calcification on the TAVI procedure.

⁷ Hughes, T.J.R. *et al.*, 2005, *Isogeometric analysis: CAD, finite elements, NURBS, exact geometry and mesh refinement*, Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering.

Multi-patch NURBS anatomical model

In this section we will discuss the details of the anatomical model used for our fast-to-evaluate simulations. We first review the fundamental ingredient of our approach, namely multi-patch *non-uniform B-splines* (NURBS). Subsequently, we outline how this geometry parametrisation technology is used to represent the aorta and leaflets.

Multi-patch non-uniform rational B-splines (NURBS)

Splines are the industry standard in *computer-aided design* (CAD) tools, on account of their ability to accurately represent complex shapes with relatively few parameters (control points). Moreover, splines form the backbone of IGA, a state-of-the-art finite element technique that is especially suitable for simulating geometrically complex systems. The advantages of splines in representing geometries, especially when compared to piecewise linear geometry representations (such as STL), do conceptually carry over to natural systems, but software tools to generate such spline-based geometries are not as mature as engineering CAD systems. In this deliverable, a spline model for the aorta and leaflets is developed. Given the prevalent use of piecewise linear geometry representations in this kind of biological systems, we aim for backward-compatibility of our fast-to-evaluate model, in the sense that such geometry parametrisations should also be compatible with our model.

Various spline techniques have been developed over the past decades⁸, but the most widely adopted spline technology is *NURBS*. The main advantages of NURBS are: (i) one obtains an explicitly parametrised geometry, with control over detail/resolution and smoothness; (ii) the accurate representation of specific surfaces (e.g., circles, cylinders, and spheres); and (iii) the ability to perform refinements that preserve the representation of the geometry. The algorithms and associated software implementations for creating and editing NURBS are very mature⁹.

Figure 2 shows the simplest example of a NURBS in the form of a smooth curve. A NURBS curve is constructed by the specification of a knot vector (which encodes the underlying interpolation functions) and a control net, *i.e.*, a non-conforming mesh that controls the geometry (the red mesh in Figure 2). An essential aspect of NURBS is that each control point (*i.e.*, a vertex of the control net) is supplemented with a weight. This weight controls the local shape of the curve and can be used to alter the geometry in a convenient manner (as we will discuss below for the parametrisation of the moving leaflets). Figure 3 illustrates the usage of NURBS for a two-dimensional surface, which requires the specification of a knot vector per parametric direction. The order of the NURBS can be selected independently for each of the parametric directions. In the left subfigure of Figure 3, a quadratic description is used for the tangential direction, whereas a linear radial parametrisation is considered. In the right subfigure of Figure 3, both directions are parametrised using quadratic NURBS.

⁸ Rogers D. F., 2001, An introduction to NURBS: with historical perspective. The Morgan Kaufmann Series in Computer Graphics. San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers, 2001.

⁹ Piegl, L. & Tiller, W., 1996, The NURBS book, Springer Science & Business Media.

Figure 2: An illustration of a two-dimensional control net (in red) of a NURBS curve (in blue).

Figure 3: Comparison of a linear (left) and quadratic (right) through-the-thickness NURBS patch. The gray area indicates a multi-patch geometry with patch vertices shown in black squares and the control net of each patch shown in red.

Depending on the complexity of a geometry, it can be constructed with a single patch or multiple patches. The difference between a single- and multi-patch is shown in Figure 4. Simple geometries, for example, e.g., geometries with a topology equal to a square, can be represented by a single patch. However, topologically more complex geometries are typically represented using a combination of multiple NURBS patches. Additionally, multiple patches provide a setup for local refinements (see Figure 4), although alternative local refinement strategies have been developed in the context of IGA^{10,11}. In the case of multi-patch geometries, it is necessary to ensure continuity across the patches. The most common technique to ensure continuity is to merge the control points at the patch interfaces.

¹⁰ Giannelli C. *et al.*, 2011, A hierarchical approach to adaptive local refinement in isogeometric analysis, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*.

¹¹ Giannelli C. *et al.* 2016, THB-splines: An effective mathematical technology for adaptive refinement in geometric design and isogeometric analysis, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*.

Figure 4: Comparison of a single-patch (left) and multi-patch (right) geometry. The grey area indicates a geometry constructed using a patch with its boundaries shown in black. Patch vertices are marked as black squares.

Anatomical model of the aorta and the aortic valves

We have developed a parametrised multi-patch NURBS template for the aorta and the leaflets, as illustrated in Figure 5 and Figure 6. The template geometry is parametrised considering the most prominent geometric features as identified in SIMCor virtual patient generator¹², namely the radius and length of (i) the *sino tubular junction* (STJ); (ii) the sinus, and (iii) the *left ventricular outflow track* (LVOT). This means that for any selection of these parameters, a template geometry can be generated. Our template generation procedure is implemented in the Python-based open-source numerical analysis library Nutils¹³.

The design of the parameterised template involves careful selection of patch subdivision and control net configuration. In relation to the design of the aortic wall in Figure 5, the key aspects are:

- The patches must be chosen so that the leaflets are seamlessly attached to the wall. This is achieved by connecting a patch to each of the leaflets, and a corresponding patch to the aortic wall to form a sinus.
- For various cross-sections of the aorta, the idealised template is assumed to be circular. This exploits the ability of NURBS to accurately create circular segments. Specifically, non-uniform control point weights are used.

While the aortic wall in our fast-to-evaluate model is stationary, capturing the motion of the leaflets is essential. In Figure 6 we show the leaflet geometry and its control net at three different opening levels. The opening level is parameterised by the distance between the leaflet and the centerline of the aorta, Δ . As can be seen in Figure 6.a, when the leaflet is opened, the upper edge of the leaflet is modelled by a circle segment, which is achieved by assigning a weight of $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ to the center control point. When the leaflet is closed, as shown in Figure 6.c, the required shape is very pinched, in the limit approaching a sharp kink at the centerline. To create this shape, besides moving the control point toward the centerline, we also alter the weight of the central control point. By assigning a large weight to this point, the high curvature edge is formed. To mimic the motion of the leaflet, the control point positions and weights are interpolated based on the opening parameter Δ , creating a blending of the two extreme cases discussed above.

¹² From SIMCor D7.6 Proof of principle of the complete virtual patient generator

¹³Gertjan van Zwieten *et al.*, 2022, Nutils (7.0) Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6006701>

Figure 5: Parameterised multi-patch NURBS template of the aorta. Each colour represents a patch, black lines represent the control net, and the dots represent the control points.

Figure 6: Top and side views of parameterised multi-patch NURBS template of the aortic valves. Each colour represents a patch, black lines represent the control net, and the dots represent the control points.

The developed multi-patch NURBS model is patient specific, in the sense that the key anatomical features of the (virtual) patient are taken into account. At this point, shape details, e.g., coming from scan data, are not yet taken into consideration in the template. The technology to do this is available,

and has been applied, for example, in the context of patient-specific heart models^{14,15}. While the interest in and relevance of geometric details in high-fidelity simulations is evident, this is not naturally the case for the fast-to-evaluate model considered in this deliverable. From a modelling perspective, the geometry errors are insignificant in comparison to the errors of the physiological model. Considering the global approximation characteristics of the fast-to-evaluate model, the inclusion of geometric details based on scan data may not significantly affect the results and could hence only increase the computational complexity of the method. Further study of the incorporation of geometric details is therefore warranted.

¹⁴ Patient-specific simulation of the human heart – Scan-based isogeometric analysis: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TArw2tcK7qI>

¹⁵ Verberne, L. P. B, (2022), Development of patient-specific geometries for isogeometric cardiac modeling: Creating of a spline-fitting algorithm to obtain a patient-specific geometry of the left ventricle based on echocardiograms, MSc Thesis, Eindhoven University of Technology.

Fast-to-evaluate TAVI model

In this section we detail the fast-to-evaluate TAVI model. We first introduce the physiological model, after which we discuss various algorithmic aspects. We finally discuss how the parameters of the fast-to-evaluate model can be derived from high-fidelity models, considering the leaflet stiffnesses as a prototypical case.

TAVI implantation model

Problem setup and solution algorithm

In our fast-to-evaluate model, the implantation procedure is mimicked by a cylindrical stent which expands around a guidewire, as illustrated in Figure 7. The guidewire can translate and rotate at the origin of the coordinate system $x = 0$. The starting point of the guidewire is positioned at $x_o(u, v)$, where u and v are the translations from the origin of the coordinate system in y and z direction, respectively. The rotation of the guidewire along the z and y axes are denoted by θ and ψ , respectively. We model the expanding stent as a series of n_{stent} expanding catheter segments, ranging from L_1 to L_2 ; see Figure 7. The radius of each segment of the catheter is denoted by $R_{\text{seg},j}(t)$ where j is the segment index, with the rate of expansion denoted by \dot{R}_i .

To model the time-dependent deployment process, we track the quasi-static mechanical equilibrium of the stent at each time step in the expansion process. The mechanical model is detailed in the next section. While the mechanical equilibrium is treated implicitly, *i.e.*, the response forces are adjusted for the displacement increment computed in the considered time step, the detection of the contact points is explicit. This means that the contact points are determined at the beginning of a time step and are not updated within a time step. Moreover, within a time step, the motion of the guidewire is linearised, reducing the problem to a linear system of equations. When a segment gets into contact with either the leaflets or the wall, the expansion rate for that segment is reduced to avoid violating the maximum allowable response force or oversizing. The simulation is terminated when the expansion rate of all segments is reduced below a specified threshold.

When the solution result is obtained, we consider two post-processing operations to acquire the results. First, the segment representation of the expanding stent is smoothed using a B-spline representation. To do this, a B-spline convolution operation is considered¹⁶. Secondly, the paravalvular leakage area is computed for a selection of cross-sectional planes orthogonal to the guidewire.

¹⁶ Divi, S. C. *et al.*, 2022, Topology-preserving scan-based immersed isogeometric analysis, Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering.

Figure 7: Schematic illustration of the fast-to-evaluate model replicating the deployment procedure. The guidewire (of length L) is shown in blue, the expanding (segmented) catheter (of length L_2) is shown in (opaque) yellow, and the smoothed surface of the catheter is shown in yellow. The translational and rotational resistances are shown in green and brown, respectively. The contact forces due to aortic wall (F_w) and leaflet (F) are shown in the zoom boxes. Note that this illustration is presented in two-dimensions for the sake of clarity, but the actual model is three-dimensional.

Mechanical equilibrium – contact modelling

In our mechanical equilibrium model, we assume inertia forces to be negligible. This means that the forces exerted on the guidewire and stent must be in equilibrium. In our model we consider three types of forces, namely the forces exerted at the origin of the guidewire, the forces exerted by contact between the stent segments and the arterial wall, and the forces exerted by the contact between the stent and the leaflets. Details regarding each of these forces are discussed below.

The translational resistance of the guidewire is modelled through a pair of springs with stiffness, k_u and k_v , which are unloaded when $u = u_0$ and $v = v_0$, respectively. The rotational resistance of the guidewire system is modelled through a pair of rotational springs with stiffness, k_θ and k_ψ , which are unloaded when $\theta = \theta_0$ and $\psi = \psi_0$, respectively.

The contact between the expanding stent and the artery is modelled by considering a set of points $\mathcal{W} = \{\mathbf{y}_i\}_{i=1}^{n_p}$ on the artery wall. The signed distance between a point $\mathbf{y}_i \in \mathcal{W}$ and the expanding stent is given by $\Delta_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) = R_{seg,j}(t) - |\mathbf{d}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi)|$, where $\mathbf{d}_i = \mathbf{y}_i - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi)$ and the closest point to \mathbf{y}_i along the guidewire is $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi)$. When the distance is positive, there is a contact between the point and the stent, and the force exerted on the stent is equal to $\mathbf{F}_w(u, v, \theta, \psi) = -k_w \Delta_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) \mathbf{n}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi)$, k_w is a parameter representing the wall stiffness and $\mathbf{n}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) = \frac{\mathbf{d}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi)}{|\mathbf{d}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi)|}$. When the distance is negative, there is no contact between the point and the stent.

The contact between the expanding stent and the leaflets is modelled by considering a set of three contact points, $\mathcal{L} = \{\mathbf{l}_i\}_{i=1}^3$, each point representing one of the leaflets. Each leaflet point is assumed

to move in a direction \mathbf{m}_i , corresponding to the blended spline model discussed above. In practice, the direction, \mathbf{m}_i , is set to be along a line orthogonal to the centreline of the NURBS template. The deformation of the leaflet point, Δ_i , also used above to parametrise the moving leaflet, the follows from the quadratic equation

$$|\mathbf{l}_i^\perp - \mathbf{x}_o^\perp + \mathbf{m}_i^\perp \Delta_i|^2 = R_i^2,$$

where $\mathbf{l}_i^\perp = \mathbf{l}_i - (\mathbf{l}_i \cdot \mathbf{t}_o)\mathbf{t}_o$, $\mathbf{x}_o^\perp = \mathbf{x}_o - (\mathbf{x}_o \cdot \mathbf{t}_o)\mathbf{t}_o$, and $\mathbf{m}_i^\perp = \mathbf{m}_i - (\mathbf{m}_i \cdot \mathbf{t}_o)\mathbf{t}_o$, with $\mathbf{t}_o = \mathbf{t}(\theta_o, \psi_o)$ the tangent vector. Under normal circumstances, when in contact, only one of the solutions to this quadratic equation will be positive. The other solution will be negative and non-physical (corresponding to an inverted stent). The force exerted by a leaflet point on the stent segment is given by $\mathbf{F}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) = -k_l \Delta_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) \mathbf{n}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi)$, where k_l is evaluated from a stiffness model for the leaflet (presented in the stiffness dependency section).

With all the forces specified, the quasi-static equilibrium position of the guidewire system is governed by

$$r_u(u, v, \theta, \psi) := k_u(u - u_0) + \sum_{i=1}^{n_p} \mathbf{F}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) \cdot \mathbf{e}_y = 0,$$

$$r_v(u, v, \theta, \psi) := k_v(v - v_0) + \sum_{i=1}^{n_p} \mathbf{F}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) \cdot \mathbf{e}_z = 0,$$

$$r_\theta(u, v, \theta, \psi) := k_\theta(\theta - \theta_0) + \sum_{i=1}^{n_p} \mathbf{M}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) \cdot \mathbf{e}_z = 0,$$

$$r_\psi(u, v, \theta, \psi) := k_\psi(\psi - \psi_0) + \sum_{i=1}^{n_p} \mathbf{M}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) \cdot \mathbf{e}_y = 0,$$

where the moments are defined as $\mathbf{M}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) \times \mathbf{F}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi)$ with $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) = \bar{\mathbf{x}}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi) + R_{seg,j}(t) \mathbf{n}_i(u, v, \theta, \psi)$. To compute the solution $\mathbf{a} = (u, v, \theta, \psi)$ to the nonlinear set of equations $\mathbf{r} = (r_u, r_v, r_\theta, r_\psi)$ specified above, we consider an incremental solution procedure, where the forces and moments are linearised around the solution of the previous time step. The detection of contact points is also considered only at the start of each time step.

Implementation

The model outlined above has been implemented in Python, leveraging the spline functionality provided by the Nutils package. To achieve good model performance, it is essential that the force calculations (and its linearisation) in all contact points is done efficiently. In an interpreted language, like Python, this makes it crucial to properly vectorise the operations, *i.e.*, to not consider a loop over all contact points. With our current implementation (strongly based on Numpy¹⁷) we can consider models with 200 potential contact points and solve the mechanical equilibrium in approximately 0.01 seconds. Typically, our simulations require 100-200 time steps, surmounting to a total simulation time of 1-2 seconds. It is important to note that this simulation time does not include detailed post-processing (e.g., 3D visualisation), but merely the evaluation of the stent displacement parameters and segment expansion radii. Considering the complexity of the considered model, it is realistic to pursue an implementation in a high-performance language (e.g., C++ or Julia), which is expected to yield a significant performance improvement.

Stiffness modelling

The developed model requires the specification of stiffness parameters for the artery wall and the leaflets. As outlined in the workflow discussed in the *Introduction*, these parameters can be estimated from high-fidelity models, possibly with the application of a ROM. As a prototypical example of the envisioned concept, we here consider the case of estimating the stiffness parameters for a leaflet. We

¹⁷ Harris, C.R., Millman, K.J., van der Walt, S.J. *et al.*, 2020, Array programming with NumPy, Nature.

emphasise that these results are intended to demonstrate the workflow, and that more accurate models and ROM approaches should be developed to improve the overall simulation workflow.

Figure 8: Schematic of the numerical experiments to study the leaflet stiffness. The leaflet (Ω_L) in its closed position is pushed by a semi-cylinder (Ω_B) representing the TAVI device.

To obtain a realistic response of the leaflets, we have performed high-fidelity simulations (based on solid-shell contact model using Ansys Mechanical/Explicit solver) on a native aortic leaflet during TAVI placement. An average patient geometry is created based on a patient data set (obtained from CHA, see in D6.2 - Database for anatomy and function based on preclinical and clinical data (CHA, M12)). The deformation of a single leaflet during TAVI placement is investigated using the numerical setup shown in Figure 8. The dependence of the leaflet stiffness on the length (shown in Figure 8), thickness and elastic modulus of the leaflet is investigated based on reaction forces and displacements of the leaflet, see Figure 9. Based on this study, the mean stiffness of leaflet is estimated as 2.8×10^{-3} N/mm, which is used in the simulations presented in the remainder of this report.

Figure 9: Stiffness dependency study with various leaflet lengths (shown in Figure 8), thicknesses and Young's moduli.

Results

In this section, we demonstrate the developed fast-to-evaluate model. We first perform a validation study based on a comparison with a high-fidelity model. Subsequently, we demonstrate the capability of the model for predicting patient-specific treatment outcomes.

Validation and comparison

As discussed above, the goal of the developed model is to obtain a quick initial estimation of the global characteristics of the implantation procedure. These model outcomes are, of course, also computable through high-fidelity simulations, making it possible to perform a direct comparison. With respect to this comparison, we would like to note that (i) the model parameters of the high-fidelity model and the fast-to-evaluate model cannot always be matched, especially when these relate to the material behaviour. This evidently complicates the direct comparison of the results, although a satisfactory set of matching parameters has been obtained. (ii) The output of the computationally expensive high-fidelity model is much more detailed than the one obtained via the fast-to-evaluate model. The comparison of the aspects to be predicted by the fast-to-evaluate model is logical from a validation point of view, but the richness of the output of the high-fidelity model should not be underappreciated. As already discussed, for interesting cases (e.g., cases with high paravalvular leakage areas) identified by the fast-to-evaluate model, running the corresponding high-fidelity model shall be warranted.

Here, we compare the fast-to-evaluate model with the simulations performed by PHI and presented in D8.6. These simulations consider the TAVI procedure in a convergent LVOT virtual geometry, as shown in Figure 10. Note that this geometry is represented by a surface triangulation. The workflow of these high-fidelity simulations is detailed in D8.6. The high-fidelity simulations are performed in the software HyperMesh, using the RADIOSS solver. This software is based on the finite element method, using explicit time integration and contact detection. A self-expandable TAVI stent is considered, which is first crimped into a catheter. The catheter is then gradually removed, whereupon the deployment of the stent begins. Expansion continues until the forces exerted by the artery wall and leaflets become big enough to counteract the expansion force of the self-extendable stent. The most prominent material parameters used for the high-fidelity finite element simulation are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Material parameters used for the high-fidelity finite element simulation.

Part	Density [kg/mm ³]	Elastic modulus [MPa]	Poisson ratio
Aorta / leaflets	1 e-9	2	0.4
TAVI	6.45 e-9	65000	0.3
Catheter / GC	1 e-9	50000	0.3

The fast-to-evaluate model is based on the same STL geometry as used for the high-fidelity model. The wall contact points used in the model are based on the vertices of the STL mesh. To match the problem setup of the high-fidelity simulation, we consider a guidewire length of $L = 50$ mm. In its crimped state, the radius of all segments of the stent is equal to 0.2 mm. A fixed expansion rate of 10 mm/s is considered. The stiffness parameters of the guidewire system are taken as $k_u = 0.1$ N/mm, $k_\theta = k_u (L/2)^2 = 62.5$ N/mm. For the wall stiffness and the leaflet stiffnesses we take $k_w = 1$ N/mm and $k_l = 2.8 \times 10^{-3}$ N/mm, respectively. The leaflet stiffnesses are based on the ROM simulations considered above, while the wall stiffness is set to be significantly higher than that of the leaflets. A total of four stent segments is considered. Expansion of the segments is monitored with time intervals of $\Delta t = 0.01$ s. A maximum oversizing of 1 mm is allowed, and expansion is stopped when the rate of radius expansion drops below 0.001 mm/s. The final solution is obtained in 157 steps, taking approximately 2 s to compute.

Final deployment comparison

The deployment process for the fast-to-evaluate model is shown in Figure 10 for 4 time steps. Figure 10a shows the initial configuration, where the stent has a uniform radius of 0.2 mm. Initially, the fast-to-evaluate model mimics a uniform expansion of the stent. Until the stent touches the artery wall, at around time step 50 as shown in Figure 10b, the guidewire remains in the original position. When the stent touches the wall, the exerted force translates and rotates the stent, while the radius of the stent keeps on expanding. Expansion of the radius stops at the moment that a stent segment becomes constrained by the artery wall, as is the case for the left most stent segment in Figure 10c. At this point the rotation and translation of the stent also become largely constrained. While the stent is constrained on the left at this point, in the centre it can still counteract until the forces exerted by the leaflets and the wall on the right also constrain the expansion of the other segments. The final stent position, corresponding to $u = -0.18$ mm, $v = 3.39$ mm, $\theta = 2.89^\circ$, $\psi = 3.99^\circ$, and stent deformation is shown Figure 10d.

Figure 10: TAVI implantation procedure at different time steps. The stent is represented by the yellow cylinder. The reference and transformed guidewire are shown in blue and the aortic wall is shown in red.

Figure 11 shows a direct comparison of the final stent deployment between the fast-to-evaluate model (shown in yellow) and the high-fidelity model (shown by the black stent wireframe). This comparison conveys that the fast-to-evaluate model is capable of representing the most important mechanisms that determine the position and expansion of the stent. The tilted position caused by the contact with the artery wall is observed to resemble the high-fidelity result. The narrowing of the stent near the position of the leaflets (indicated with a green arrow in Figure 11) is also captured well, as is the final radius of the stent. Evidently, there are also notable differences between the results. Most prominently, with the current settings of the fast-to-evaluate model, the significant increase in radius around the tips of the leaflets is smeared out in comparison to the high-fidelity model. We expect that optimisation of the model parameters can improve the match. However, based on the simulation of

an extensive number of parameters (also see the sensitivity analysis presented below), the displayed result already provides a realistic impression of the predictive capabilities of the fast-to-evaluate model.

Figure 11: Comparison of the fast-to-evaluate model (yellow) and high-fidelity model (black wireframe).

Sensitivity analysis of the model parameters

Since the parameter identification of the fast-to-evaluate model is not trivial, it is important to understand how these affect the simulation results. Therefore, we analyse the sensitivity of the result in relation to the most important model parameters.

Figure 12 summarises the results of variations in the stiffness parameters. Uniform distributions are assumed for the wall stiffness, k_w , and the linear spring stiffness, k_u . For both the wall stiffness and the linear stiffness, the minimum value was set to 1 N/mm and the maximum value to 10^3 N/mm. A total of 512 simulations was performed using a quasi-random sample (using Sobol sequences) from these distributions. Figure 12 shows the histograms for the outcome of the solution variables. The results show that in about 95% of the cases a solution is found that is very similar to the reference solution considered above. This is to be expected, as the final position of the stent is determined by the way it is constrained inside the artery, which limits the influence of the stiffness parameters. For a small number of realisations, the stiffness settings cause minor deviations from the reference simulation. Only a few parameter settings produced results that do not appear to be sensible, e.g., due to extreme rotations of the guidewire.

In Figure 13 we present the results of a sensitivity study in which the origin of the guidewire is randomly altered. In this case, all the stiffnesses are assumed as equal to the reference case, but the guidewire is moved along the z-axis. The offset is taken from 4 to 8 mm. The results show that the model is capable of compensating for the offset, as the spring associated with the z-direction is deformed in correspondence with the offset. This can be seen from the uniform distribution of the solution variable v , with magnitudes closely resembling the offset. This result is again expected, as with the selected stiffness settings the constraints imposed by the wall contact and the contact with the leaflets have a strong influence on the final result.

Figure 12: Distribution of displacements (u , v) and rotations (θ , ψ) with different aortic wall (k_w) and linear stiffnesses (k_u) varying from 1 to 10^3 N/mm, $k_\theta = k_u (L/2)^2$, and with no offset along the z-axis. Most simulations have solutions of approximately $u = -0.18$ mm, $v = 2.5$ mm, $\theta = 2.8^\circ$ and $\psi = 4.5^\circ$ demonstrating less sensitivity to the wall and linear stiffness parameters.

The sensitivity results presented above convey that the fast-to-evaluate model can be operated in a parameter regime where it is largely insensitive to the stiffness parameters and initial position parameters. This is an important observation, as the determination (or calibration) of these parameters is not a trivial task. The uncertainty analyses presented in this section demonstrate the robustness of the fast-to-evaluate model, but it is noted that, although rare, outlier results are sometimes obtained. Careful result inspection is therefore always necessary, and it is noted that automated solution checks could help identify possibly problematic simulations. Furthermore, considering the speed with which the fast-to-evaluate model can be run, we advise to always sample a number of parameters, thereby obtaining better insight into the parametric uncertainty and solution robustness.

Figure 13: Distribution of displacements (u , v) and rotations (θ , ψ) with different initial locations of implantation (x_0) varying from 0 to 4.5 mm along z-axis and with $k_w = 1$ N/mm, $k_u = 0.1$ N/mm, $k_\theta = k_u (L/2)^2 = 62.5$ N/mm. Most simulations have solutions in the magnitude $u = -0.18$ mm, $\theta = 2.8^\circ$ and $\psi = 4^\circ$, demonstrating less sensitivity to the guidewire location. The displacement v is uniformly distributed between 4 – 8 mm due to high sensitivity to the offset along z-axis from 0 to 4.5 mm.

Besides the physical model parameters considered in the study above, the fast-to-evaluate model also has various numerical parameters. The most prominent numerical parameter is the time step size, Δt . In Figure 14, the influence of the time step size on the result is shown, considering a time step range from 0.1 s to 0.04 s. It is clearly observed the solution converges under time step refinement, with results becoming virtually independent of the time step size for $\Delta t < 0.01$ s. Even for larger step sizes, the obtained results are close to the converged result. This indicates that the developed model is robust with respect to the time step size.

Figure 14: Displacements (u , v) and rotation (θ , ψ) of the TAVI with different time step size (Δt). A clear convergence is observed for all parameters from $\Delta t = 0.01$ [s], which is considered in all the simulations presented in this deliverable.

Patient-specific analysis based on the idealised NURBS model

In this section we assess the fast-to-evaluate model through the spline-based *parameterised* geometry. The parameters for this study are based on the average patient data from CHA (D6.2) and fall within the bounds of the virtual cohort generator developed in D7.6 - *Proof of principle of the complete virtual patient generator (TUE, M24)*. The geometric parameters used are listed in Table 2. All other parameters are the same of the validation case considered above. Below we consider two cases, *i.e.*, a case resembling a patient without calcifications on the leaflets, and a case where a patient has severe calcifications on one of the leaflets.

Description	Symbol	Value [mm]
Length of guidewire	L	50
Length of catheter	L_2	55
Radius of STJ	R_STJ	12
Height of STJ	H_STJ	25
Radius of sinus	R_SIN	15
Height of sinus	H_SIN	12
Radius of LVOT	R_LVOT	10
Height of LVOT	H_LVOT	20

Table 2: List of geometric parameters and selected values for the numerical experiments.

Figure 15: Stages of TAVI implantation in a parameterised multi-patch NURBS geometry. The TAVI device is represented by the yellow cylinder, the reference and transformed guidewire is shown in blue and the aortic wall is shown in red. As this is an axisymmetric geometry with the same leaflet stiffnesses (i.e., $k_{l_1} = k_{l_2} = k_{l_3} = 2.8 \times 10^{-3}$ N/mm) for all the three leaflets, there is no guidewire displacement and rotation.

Non-calcified leaflets

We first consider the case in which there is no calcification of the leaflets, which we mimic by taking the same stiffness value for all leaflets, viz. $k_{l_1} = k_{l_2} = k_{l_3} = 2.8 \times 10^{-3}$ N/mm. Figure 15 shows the deployment process predicted by the fast-to-evaluate model. On account of the axisymmetric setup considered in this case, the position and orientation of the guidewire and stent does not change in the deployment process. The final radius of the stent is determined by two factors. In places where the stent touches the artery wall, the specified oversizing constrains the final position of the stent, as can be seen on the left and right boundaries of the stent in Figure 15d. In the centre of the stent, where it is in contact with the leaflets, the response force exerted by the leaflets on the stent determine its final shape.

Compared to the validity study considered above, the NURBS geometry used here allows us to track the deformation of the leaflets. Figure 16 shows the same deployment process as Figure 15, but highlights the leaflet deformation. Figure 16 provides a good illustration of the NURBS representation of the leaflets in motion, showing a sharp radius when the leaflets are closed, and a larger radius when fully opened.

Figure 16: Stages of the leaflet deformation during the TAVI implantation procedure.

Figure 17: The slices considered for investigation of the paravalvular leakage area, as indicated by the solid red lines.

The paravalvular leakage areas, defined as the cross-sectional areas between the aortic wall and the catheter, are computed in the four planes orthogonal to the guidewire; see Figure 17. The artery wall and stent surface corresponding to the four cross-sections are shown in Figure 18. The slice locations, measured as the distances between the origin of the guidewire and the considered plane, are listed in Table 3. For the idealised case considered here, it is observed that the maximum paravalvular leakage area is obtained around the sinuses. This is clearly reflected by the cross-sectional plots in Figure 18. We note that in the presented results, the leaflets are not considered. The leaflets do affect the paravalvular leakage, but a further study on how to incorporate their effect in the current model is required.

Plane distance (s) [mm]	Paravalvular area [mm ²]		Increase in area
	Idealised	Calcified	
20	295.58	600.85	103.2 %
30	423.07	733.85	73.4 %
40	171.19	484.17	182.8 %
50	19.33	255.44	1221.5 %

Table 3: Paravalvular leakage areas corresponding to the idealized and calcified leaflet cases.

Figure 18: Schematic view of the aortic wall (red) and catheter (yellow) of the idealized parameterised geometry at a plane orthogonal to the guidewire and at a distance s from the origin at the end of deployment. The corresponding areas are presented in Table 3.

Calcified leaflet

We now consider the case in which a single leaflet is calcified. This testcase should be seen as a proof-of-concept for calcification study. In the fast-to-evaluate model we mimic calcification by an increase in leaflet stiffness, in this case by setting $k_{l_1} = 100 \text{ N/mm}$. Figure 19 illustrates the TAVI procedure for this case. The stiffer leaflet, positioned at the top in Figure 19, forces the guidewire out of position, most clearly seen in Figure 19c and Figure 19d. This results in a completely different type of contact with the wall compared to the ideal case considered above.

The out-of-positioning of the stent has a significant effect on the paravalvular leakage. Figure 20 considers the same cross-sectional planes as for the idealised geometry. Comparison with Figure 18 shows notable differences, where the most important observation is that at no point along the guidewire there is a good seal between the stent and the artery wall. This is also reflected by comparison of the leakage areas in Table 3, where at $s = 50 \text{ mm}$ a small leakage area is observed for the ideal scenario, but a dramatic increase at that location is observed on account of the modelled calcification.

Figure 19: Stages of the TAVI implantation in a parameterised multi-patch NURBS geometry with a higher stiffness for one of the leaflets, replicating calcification. A clear misalignment of the TAVI device is observed (in panel d) due to the calcified leaflet which has a considerably higher stiffness ($k_{l_1} = 100 \text{ N/mm}$) compared to other two leaflets ($k_{l_2} = k_{l_3} = 2.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N/mm}$).

Note however, that the restriction of the calcified leaflet on the TAVI expansion is very strong in this example. While severe calcifications that restrict movement altogether might occur, these usually prohibit use of the TAVI procedure. Nonetheless, the example clearly demonstrates the viability of the approach to account for local differences in tissue properties, such as stiffness.

Figure 20: Schematic of the aortic wall (red) and catheter (yellow) of the idealized parameterised geometry at a plane orthogonal to the guidewire and at a distance s from the origin at the end of deployment. The corresponding areas are presented in Table 3.

Concluding remarks and outlook

Concluding remarks

In this deliverable, a *fast-to-evaluate TAVI model* was developed. By its capability of providing global characteristics for the TAVI procedure in near real-time, in the overall simulation workflow of SIMCor, this model can be used to estimate treatment effects on large virtual cohorts. The model parameters of the developed fast-to-evaluate model can either be calibrated based on (simulated) data or be derived from high-fidelity models (possibly using a ROM approach).

The developed model derives its computational efficiency from two key ingredients, a spline-based anatomical model and a discrete contact mechanics model. For the anatomical model, use is made of a multi-patch NURBS. This spline technology allows for the construction of an accurate geometry, parametrized by patient-specific properties such as the length of the leaflets, the dimensions of the STJ, sinus and LVOT. For the mechanical model, a discrete set of points (for the arterial wall and leaflets) is used where contact with the expanding stent can be monitored. The balance of forces is solved implicitly, as this is essential for the stability of the time-stepping algorithm. Detection of the contact points and geometric linearisation is treated explicitly, improving the computational efficiency of the simulations.

The simplifying assumptions considered in this work to achieve the high computational performance (near real-time simulations) inevitably reduce the solution detail in comparison to high-fidelity simulations. For the global solution characteristics, the fast-to-evaluate model can be compared to high fidelity simulations. In this study, a comparison was made with a simulation performed using an explicit finite element simulation in HyperMesh (part of *D8.6*). This comparison demonstrates that a good correspondence is observed in terms of the positioning of the stent and the final shape of the stent, despite the significant difference in computational effort between the two simulations (hours vs seconds).

The developed tool can be used to predict patient-specific treatment outcomes. In this study we have provided a demonstration of this capability by comparing two cases: one patient with healthy leaflets, and one with a calcified leaflet. The fast-to-evaluate model provides insight into the positioning of the stent and, through post-processing operations, quantifies the areas subject to paravalvular leakage. The fast-to-evaluate model is shown to mimic the negative effects of calcifications on the TAVI treatment.

Outlook

Future developments of the fast-to-evaluate model include:

- The model should be included in the VRE developed in WP3. Conceptually, the developed model is compatible with the input formats provided by the virtual cohort generator (*D7.6*), which is already part of the VRE. Further development on the software interface is required for this, however. The involved efforts highly depend on the level of (software) integration required.
- Improved estimates for the parameters of the fast-to-evaluate model can likely be acquired from high-fidelity models. As part of *D8.7*, a more advanced ROM for the leaflet parameters can be developed. Possibly, other model developments in SIMCor, e.g., on the influence of calcifications, can also provide meaningful quantitative inputs for the model presented here.
- The indicator for paravalvular leakage as currently implemented in the fast-to-evaluate model is purely geometric, *i.e.*, it only identifies the cross-sectional areas through which leakage can occur. The current implementation should be amended with the consideration of the leaflets in this geometric indicator. A more detailed, but still fast, estimator, e.g., based on Hagen-

Poiseuille estimates, can be implemented to obtain improved insights on the treatment outcome. Again, reduced-order modelling concepts can be used to enhance the outcome results of the fast-to-evaluate model, for example, by using the leakage model of *D8.6* to quantify the flow leakage based on the currently obtained geometric indicator.

- In the overall SIMCor workflow, the fast-to-evaluate model is to be applied in a virtual cohort analysis. The model can add virtual treatment outcome indicators to the virtual patient generator already implemented. Successful application of the model in this virtual cohort setting also hinges on the ability to properly select/train the parameters of the fast-to-evaluate model. The sensitivity study presented herein indicates that this should be feasible for the most important model parameters, but details of this parameter calibration shall be investigated.